
In defence of interview as a skill of social understanding

Lupicinio Íñiguez

Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona

SYMPOSIUM: Conversational Processes in Social Interaction.

Xth. GENERAL MEETING of the EUROPEAN ASSOCIATION OF EXPERIMENTAL SOCIAL PSYCHOLOGY

Lisboa, September 1993

I should begin my talk saying that the title of this paper it is not any more the one you can read in the abstract book, but "**In defence of interview as a skill of social understanding**". This change is due to my aim of enphasazing the utility of "artificial interviews" as a way of social understanding. This has become my main objective because of the increasing maniqueistic differentiation between good and bad critical social psychologist, a distinction depending on a right or wrong approach to the voice of people.

Indeed, once communication and arguments between qualitative and quantitative approaches are not possible any more, unable as they are to overcome the theoretical, epistemological and methodological gap, we have moved the oratorial and rhetorical exercise of the discussion to the arena of "being more natural than any other". To unmask this, in my opinion, false controversy should be, in this paper, one of my most important aims.

So, I am going to claim that individual and group interviews are useful research and socially relevant procedures because they are, as any other social situations, capable of being described and analyzed.

The different analytical devices developed under the general label of "Discourse Analysis" (DA) are concerned with the permanent debate between perspectives positioned around two main topics: on one hand, the definition of what is to be consider as "discourse"; and, on the other, the development of the technical instrumentalization in order to apprehend it.

I am not going to talk about what discourse is; I am only going to refer to the analytical affair.

Aside of the main practical differences between the most frequent techniques used by Discourse Analysts, they are basically grounded up: (a) the examination of previously produced text, (b) the

recorded of natural conversations (or any situation), and (c) the production of individual and group interviews.

Each of these strategies have emerged as the initial element that possibilitate the subsequent analysis; and it seems necessary to explore the principal involved in each practice. For instance:

(a) Already produced texts

I Consider this material the most close to my idea of what discourse is, and therefore, the most appropriate material for a Discursive Analysis.

Adventatges:

- . it does not matter **who** wrote the text
- . objectivize the ongoing discourses in a given time and society

Disadventatges:

- . the difficulty of building up a corpus from the multiplicity of available text
- . the, in any case, exuberance of the material you have to cope with

(b) the recording and transcription of "natural discourses" (or any situation)

Adventatges:

- . it allows the recording of what is "really" happening

Disadventatges:

- . intrusiveness and violation of privacy
- . ethical and political problems
- . exercises of domination: the only person that have the right to investigate is the researcher. Can you imagine your sister or your brother inquiring here and there about her or his neighbors? What would they be doing? To gossip?

(c) production and transcription of interviews

Advantages:

- . to put in motion the socially available discourses
- . the explicit agreement of the participants

Disadvantages:

- . You will allow me to not develop this point as much as I am interested in convince you about the goodness of this procedure.

Given this framework, I will proceed to develop my point.

The context in which the discourse "extraction" has been originated is one of the first levels of analysis in this perspective. Coherently with this consideration, we conceive the analysis of individual and group interviews as possible methodological instruments in the approximation and understanding of socio-psychological phenomena as, for instance, the specific social situation that generates different narrative, informative or explicative strategies.

This is the way I have reached this conclusion.

The context of the interview has usually been considered as an artificial situation which generates unauthentic discourses. Actually, the traditional criticism directed against questionnaires and scales have been used to denigrate the use of interview as a tool of social research.

In my opinion, this kind of criticism can only be sustained if we consider the researcher as an extraterrestrial, the participants as stupid, and the research activity as transcendental. Seriously, does any body think that two adult people are unable of jointly defining a situation as such as that of the interview while we are sure that this is perfectly possible in a spontaneous or, again, "natural" context? Do not think I just want to appeal to your beliefs, let me argue, therefore, why the interview must be considered as a social situation.

The standard view of interview

The interview has generally been defined as a survey technique, i.e., as a technique to collect different individual informations in order to built a single discourse.

As in any pragmatic situation, the interviewer asks for information to the interviewee, who builds a discourse as a result of his/her interaction with the interviewer. In this kind of procedure it is recommended that the interviewer leads the interview, searches for opinions, beliefs, habits and so on and maintains a natural position. Every interview is built from a private contract of communication (as Ghiglione 1986 says). This contract shapes the speakers common references which are validated and reinforced by the use of specific strategies.

Nevertheless, the result of the interaction is, at last apparently, paradoxal. On one hand, the interviewee's discourse is a consequence of the activation of the interviewer, and in this sense dependent of it. But on other hand, her/his discourse is, at the same time, also autonomous because it is structured looking for each own coherence following paths that have not necessarily to do with the interviewer.

Other view of interview

Yet, there can be other kinds of interviews. In my work, I have both rejected this definition of interview and this praxis. The pre-given differentiation between their roles and discourses, introduces a dynamic consisting in a development of two simultaneous strategies: one, on the interviewer's side, the overplaying in the interpretation; an other, on the interviewee's side, to mask (for a development of this topic, see Ghiglione, 1986 and Blanchet, 1991).

From my point of view, we have to substitute the dynamics ACTIVATION-ANSWER by an other of CONVERSATION, maintaining the private contract of communication. Indeed, such as I understand it, **the interview is a conversation steams from a contract of communication**. This contract specifies the agreement by which the topic of the talk comes from on interviewer's proposal. There is no restriction about what can or can not be said. The interviewer have not got to hide his/her condition because what defers his/her position in the interaction is that he/she proposes the topic, records the interview and analyzes it. All other prescriptions like the major or minor directiveness, the neutrality and so on, disappears.

In this way, it is defined a social situation with this characteristics:

- (a) The interview is a device of speech production. As we have learn from the pragmatics, the speech concerns three main functions:
 - a. to say how things are (referential function)

- b. to say what you think about things (modal function)
- c. to modify or alter the other (act function)

The first two functions are intralinguistic, and are carried out through language. The last one is extralinguistic and is carried out through complex mechanisms of interchange and interference (this is not the place to develop the form in which has to be considered the double aspect, semantic and pragmatic, that conversation and discourse analysis have to deal with)

- (b) the interview is a particular situation of social interaction structured by the relationship between the actors in a specific space-temporal and social context. This interactive situation defines the positions, the rules, the norms, the objectives and so on, as elements embedded in a context, avoiding to present the question as a one of isolating, controlling or whatever pretend to inhibit the influence of the context but to bring them into light.
- (c) it follows from all of this, that the interviewer is an active participant who incorporates into the situation his/her own background as if he or she was like another participant
- (d) and, finally, it is a conversation as any other one: a public activity sequenced in turns taken that delimitate and determine the posterior sequence and make sense from the previous sentence. Summing up, all the norms and characteristics of the conversations that, as we know, they come into surface when they fail.

We have called this kind of interview "**FULL PARTICIPATIVE**" as Pujol and myself point out in the poster exposed in this meeting.

Besides the epistemological implications of this position and practice, some number of consequences are derived from. Some of the most important are:

- (a) As we have seen, to consider the interview as a ordinary social situation allows to incorporate to the interviewer as a participant actor. The most interesting arising consequence is that he or she carries out a double hermeneutic exercise. From one side, as an actor, interprets the situation. From the other side, as an analyst, interprets the whole situation, including him or herself as a participant actor. This reflexive analysis offers an interesting perspective as Pujol developed in his doctoral disestation (1993)

- (b) A second consequence I would like to outline, consists in that to interpret is essential the reading in the context: the social context in which the interview is produced; the context of the other text pre- co- existent; the rhetorical context in which the interventions are produced; and the co-text in which every intervention is embedded

I hope you are now convince that, finally, the uses of this kind of interviews in the research practices is not only an economic and quick way to collect information, but a coherent procedure with a non-fundamentalist and non-empiricist conception of social research